

Rethinking Nigeria's Presidential System and the Concomitant Development Trajectory

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Abstract

Democracy as is practiced in Nigeria especially the presidential version of it, is leaving much to be desired. Today, we hear and read the saga of millions of different currencies local and foreign either discovered, uncovered, hauled or forcefully recovered through activity of whistle blowers, is an indication of a sordid state of petrification of the system. All is not well with our presidential brand of democracy. This paper seeks to analyze the goings on to indicate some of the possible reasons why our system of democracy is at a cross road or perhaps endangered. Among the reasons for this paper is to point out that is Nigeria's presidential system is not re-engineered, Nigeria will continue to gravitate on the path of underdevelopment. Development can only be achieved through the adoption of tested/proven principles of development. We are recommending a rational integrated mixture of Marxism and capitalism.

Key Words: Presidential, democracy, doctrine of necessity.

Résumé

La démocratie, surtout sa version présidentielle, telle qu'elle est pratiquée au Nigeria laisse beaucoup à désirer. Force est de constater que ce système se trouve aujourd'hui dans un stade de pourriture généralisée. Voilà pourquoi l'on lit et entend des cas de plusieurs millions en monnaie locale et en devise étrangère qu'on aurait découverts ou recouverts par force à travers les activités des dénonciateurs. Notre version du présidentielisme est malade. La présente étude entend analyser ses dynamiques internes aux fins de cerner les vraies raisons qui mettent notre version de la démocratie en péril ou à la croisée des chemins.

Mots-clés: Présidentiel, Démocratie, Doctrine de nécessité

Introduction

The events in our polity in the past twelve years marking the nascent democratic dispensation in Nigeria gives every well-meaning and sensitive Nigerian both in Nigeria and in Diaspora serious cause for concern and worry. Democracy is a governmental system articulated to ensure the maximum weal and good of the generality of the populace.

The general and disheartening experience is that the democratic dividend is lopsided. Only the rich and a negligible minority of the population is being positively impacted upon in terms of their material well being. It is this concern that has necessitated this write up.

The question that readily comes to mind is, is the problem with the democratic system or with the presidential version of the democratic system. As G.O Ozumba have argued elsewhere, democracy has its ideals and any people that adopt these ideals are bound to be the better for it. The problem with the Nigerian experience is that we have adopted just

the letter and not the spirit of democracy. Democracy is a system of government that enthrones probity, accountability and empowerment of the poor because it is a government of the people, by the people and for the people. But what we have today is a warped democratic structure that is sewed to maintain the hegemony of the rich over the poor without any room for fair distribution of national resources.

The above state of affairs is worsened by the unremitting avarice and greed of the ruling class who through the presidential system have come to gloat over the majority through excessive display of the common patrimony cornered for selfish and private use at the expense of the majority of the poor for whom they are in power. This has led to the high level of impoverishment and alienation of the mass of our people. It is therefore our opinion that the presidential system of government is not only very expensive but skewed to profit the ruling class and their lackeys with an entrenched structure that facilitates the perpetuation of injustice and disproportionate distribution of the dividends of democracy. This paper therefore advocates either a restructuring of the presidential system in such a way that though an expensive system the process of its operation will rub off equally on the mass of our people or invariably a parliamentary or less bogus presidential system of government should be adopted with a drastic reduction of chains of advisers, special assistants and other nebulous and redundant positions created as drain-pipes for financial extortion and impropriety.

This paper therefore will examine the presidential system, its ideals, shortcomings and possible realistic restructuring that will make it amenable and germane to the achievement of the fairness we wish to attain in terms of justifiable distribution of natural resources. We shall comment on the place of the doctrine of necessity and how it should be employed to enhance the overall output of governance in terms of harmony, due process and propriety.

What do we mean by presidential system of government?

Presidential system of government cannot be defined in a definitive way. Rather it is an omnibus phrase depicting a system with many parameters and indices.

Presidential system of government is a governmental system that is headed by a president who is in charge of the executive and exercises great power over his cabinet who are more or less appointed by him to do his bidding. He is equipped with the veto power to thwart the opinion or the legislative policies and laws enacted by the legislature. His awesome power makes it possible for the president to become authoritarian.

In the American system from where Nigeria draws her inspiration, the presidential government is characterized by:

- (i) A president who is directly elected by the citizens (the electorate)
- (ii) The president forms his cabinet who more or less function at the instance of the president. This means that the president hires and fires his cabinet members. This means the need for unquestioned loyalty to the president. The cabinet members therefore do the bidding of the president.
- (iii) The president has the veto power to withhold assent on laws and policies recommended by the congress or the national assembly.

- (iv) The president if he has a legislature dominated by his party men can hold complete sway over the business of government. This means that policy choices become his to make at the end of the day without any opposition.
- (v) The presidential system has the three arms of government namely, the executive, the legislature and the judiciary, each arm while complementing and working in cooperation with others should at the same be expected to check and balance the others. The executive is headed by the president who appoints his cabinet of ministers, special advisers and retinue of other officers who assist him in the day to day administration of the government. The legislature is made up of the upper house (Senate) and the lower house called House of Representatives. The meeting of the combined Houses is called national assembly.
The judiciary is made up the chief justice of the federation and eminent jurists who are appointed members of the nation's supreme court.
- (vi) Other features of the presidential system is the delineation of the time line for each dispensation. It is a four year term in Nigeria. Elections determine who ascends the presidential throne and other elective offices.
- (vii) There is separation of powers between the executive, the legislature and the judiciary.
- (viii) There is independent electoral commission that is charged with the responsibility of conducting free and fair election.
- (ix) Party politics supposedly based on democratic principles is part of the huge machine we call presidential system of government.

Problems with Presidential System of Government

The presidential system of government inspite of its advantages like

- a) Predisposition to stability
 - b) Encourage wider political participation
 - c) Greater governmental control through execute laws and policies (that is, the legislature to make laws and the judiciary interpret and ensure enforcement of laws.)
 - d) There is separation of power and mutual respect of the three arms of government for one another.
 - e) Where a particular political party dominates the three arms of government there is greater harmony, agreement and removal of impediments to leadership.
 - f) There is more resilience in tackling national emergencies because the president has the power to take swift action to bring situations under control.
- Inspite of the above advantages the following disadvantages are also quite noticeable or possible:
- a. There is the tendency towards authoritarianism. The President because of the enormous powers at his disposal is likely to abuse these powers and begin to act in autocratic ways. The saying that "power corrupts but absolute power corrupts absolutely is true of the presidential system of government.
 - b. This absolute power enhances the chances of incumbent presidents entrenching themselves in power through rigging and cowering of political opposition.

- c. The zero-sumness of presidential elections makes the winner to take all while the loser takes nothing. Except in few cases where a government of national unity is put in place as a bootstrap to sustain fragile polity. This zero-sumness exacerbates attendant tension and polarization.
- d. A domineering, irrational president can trigger serious war between the executive and the legislature or the executive and the judiciary. The unjust or reckless use of the power of veto can polarize the government.
- e. The separation of powers is often cosmetic because those in power have the same interest namely looting the treasury. As members of the powerful elite there is the pact or agreement to aid one another in the looting. The Nigerian case is a mindless one because the competition is about who out steals the other and not about checks and balances. There is therefore conspiratorial silence or cosmetic fight against corruption at times the different arms trade blames against one another without any sincere intent to unravel who the perpetrators of corruption are. It is a system of steal and share to remain unconvicted.
- f. Because of the foregoing, there is very little room for accountability. Only those who fall out of favour with the president suffer witch hunt and persecution.
- g. The presidential system is very expensive with little or no consideration for the plight of the majority of the citizens who are very far from the seat of government or from its corridors. Those who are properly positioned continue to "Eat" while those who are not "in" government continue to wallow in abject poverty.
- h. It encourages god-fatherism. Money bags become very powerful and now begin to determine who rules at the different strata of governance.
- i. It encourages nepotism, ethnicity, favouritism and sectionalism. Political power means financial power for the ruler and those of his kinsmen, friends and close associates. This is why we have the saying "seek ye first the political kingdom and other things will be added unto you".
- j. Another problem associated with presidentialism is that it is difficult to change leaders and to get good leaders. Criminals who are bold, audacious and courageous eventually get into power only to explore all wicked devices to perpetuate themselves in power since the president has all the resources at his disposal, he can thwart impeachment by buying over the legislature.
- k. There is the problem of slowness in responding to the needs of the common man. There is the problem of the tyranny of the majority. The minority can only be seen but not heard. In Nigeria, rotation of power is thought only in relation to the Hausa, Fulani, the Yoruba and the Igbo. Nobody considers the minority ethnic nationalities. The controversy whether Goodluck Jonathan should run for the president is raging with ferocity because he comes from the minority ethnic group.

Presidential system of government is seen as a complex and expensive system and as such is not germane for developing nations like Nigeria which are still struggling with nation-building and infrastructural development. A country like Nigeria where corruption is both endemic and systemic, situation is worsened by the multiplication of corrupt officials, which presidentialism necessarily entails.

From the president to the local government chairman, all you have are a proliferation “triplication’ if not quadriplification” of offices all in the bid to satisfy party faithfuls, party godfathers, thugs and ethnic pressure. At the end of the day, you have a swarm of thieves milling around the executive thieves. What we have in the end is a multiplication of stealing public servants. The consequent is that the national till is depleted and there is nothing left for real governance which should impact on the ordinary citizens of our country.

Many have argued that the problem is not with the presidential system but with the base human nature. They further argue that the proliferation of offices and portfolios means more people being employed and therefore extending the largesse of governance to them. The truth is that, inspite of the unnecessary proliferation, the total number employed is still negligible in comparison with the total population of the unemployed. Again, the massive misappropriation that goes on reveals the near self centredness and wickedness that characterize our brand of corruption.

It is ridiculous for a government official to steal money which belongs to poor Nigerians only to go and buy houses in Paris, London, New York, Berlin, Tokyo and other major cities of the world that do not need further development. A stolen money which is invested in the Nigerian soil is less tragic (even though the evil is by no way excused), it is again worse when developed countries like Britain, America, USA, China, Japan, etc, send aids to us to ameliorate the sufferings of our common people and our leaders steal this money from us and repatriate the money to the banks of the nation’s from which the aids came in the first place. When they come to discover this, they begin to wonder the malady African countries are subjected to.

A nation with Kleptomaniac leadership, employing trainee Kleptomaniacs have very little room and hope for survival. There is therefore need for a complete overhaul of the status quo. The solution lies squarely with the masses who must arise, take their destinies in their hands and throw overboard the yoke of bad leadership which has dogged our steps as a nation since independence. The critical factor needed for the change is leadership. A selfless, sincere, visionary, committed and patriotic leader can turn things around within a decade. All other resource components for development are in place like natural, human, ecological, environmental and intellectual. What is needed is a God-sent leader who will transform our attitude of self-centeredness to one of patriotism and then, every other thing will fall into place.

Our predisposition and predilection for corruption then demands that we either change the system or enact laws that will trim the bogus nature of our presidential system in order to have a more manageable system. This leads us to the problem we had during the period our former president Yar’ Adua was sick, we saw political joggling, manipulations and mafia-like “abracadabra” that bordered on treachery and demonism. We thank God for the doctrine of necessity that was introduced rather belatedly by the National Assembly. Many are of the view that we should infuse a provision for the operation of the doctrine of necessity in times of great national emergency. This leads us to the consideration of the doctrine of necessity and its place in nurturing a presidential system of our dream.

Presidentialism and the Doctrine of Necessity in the Nigerian Democratic Experiment

Presidentialism we have already averred is not impracticable for Nigeria but is rather predispositional to the exacerbation of our base humane excesses. Initial poverty and sudden exposure to wealth is not germane for proper thinking especially for the stock of men who aspire to lead us in Nigeria. This is why the Holy Writ says that the earth is disquieted when “a servant reigneth and a fool when he is filled with meat” (Prov 30:22). This is why some nouveau-riche we have in the country can barricade a whole street meant for all of us in the name of marriage or funeral or chieftaincy ceremonies. One minister was celebrating the silver jubilee of his marriage while his ministry was on strike and the people he was appointed to serve were mourning because of withheld and poor salaries. This is the leadership type that we are “blessed” with in this country. The question is, what do we mean by “the doctrine of necessity?” There is the “is” and the “ought” definitions of this phrase.

The ought definition simply defines the doctrine of necessity within the purview of politics as the political device or contrivance whereby political actors respond to an emergency situation not fully or clearly provided for in the law through a ratiocinative consideration for the stability of the polity and for the common weal.

But the “is” definition of the doctrine of necessity which applies to Nigeria is the “externally propelled action of the National Assembly only on the understanding that passivity will be injurious to the life of the national assembly itself and its members”. It is action motivated by self-interest, self-preservation, self-glorification fired by political expediency and brinkmanship”.

It is an action lacking in good judgement, timeliness, patriotism and nationalism. The advent or introduction of the doctrine of necessity into the political lexicon of Nigerian politics by Senator David Mark led national assembly should be viewed as self-serving and dubious. This means that the concept of “doctrine of necessity” instead of an innocuous connotation is coming into our lexicon as a negative political contrivance.

It was the French philosopher Rene Descartes who warned that we should never trust on anything that had once, deceived us. It is in this wise that it becomes expedient and necessary that we should instead of waiting for our National Assembly to trump up a bill based on the doctrine of necessity to save us in future emergencies, we should take our destinies in our hands as Kenyans have done in enacting a new constitution where the ordinary people of Kenya now hold the sovereignty in driving their own destiny. To trust the review of our constitution in the hands of our National Assembly is to gamble with our lives and the future of our children. A passionately, infinitely interested patriotic representatives of the people should be selected to do this job of giving us a fool-proof and human based constitution which will entrench the ideals of the founding fathers of democracy into our governance. To leave governance to the chance application of the doctrine of necessity will too risky to present us as a society deserving of the least political good.

We may still retain presidentialism but there is need to have a constitution that will take care of the obvious lapses in our brand of presidentialism and have those checks and balances which must be made to work through in-built mechanism which make the inactivity of our law-makers, the executive and the judiciary a wake-up call for the civil

society. To sustain this system, a conscious, conscientious, proactive, visionary, courageous and vocal civil, society is a sine-qua-non. The ball is now in the court of civil society to say No to bad government, corruption and a self-serving democratic experiment which never thinks of the electorate but only themselves.

According to Griffith, American presidential system is a government of 'built in' restraints and as he says, these restraints force the kind of accountability that must carry conviction with it before power may be exercised by either the executive or congress (V). It does seem to me that in adopting American style governance, we concentrated on the 'form' and not on the 'spirit' or 'matter' of the system. As Kant said, cognition without content is empty and content without understanding is blind. This perhaps is why there is so much blindness and groping in the government we are running in Nigeria. He also talked about the omni-competence of the legislature. This presupposes a legislature composed of men and women of integrity. We are yet to be convinced that the Nigerian hallowed chambers are constituted as it presently is with men of integrity and selflessness. If we have them, then, they must have been drowned and submerged in the sea of passivity by the abrasive and self-seeking majority that calls the shots at the National Assembly. Lust for wealth has caged and annihilated competence. We have honourable men who only gather to turn out new devices of cornering more of the wealth of our commonwealth into their private pockets. You have a full house only when there are some largesse to share otherwise, the attendance is scanty. For the country to move forward, we need more patriotism and selflessness from our legislators at all levels of governance.

Achieving Development through Marxian and Capitalist Principles

Marxism is the philosophical cum political and economic ideology that stresses the necessity of running a just, egalitarian and welfarist system. The principle is from each according to his ability and to each according to his need. The emphasis on equitable distribution of basic resources to meet basic needs. Capitalist principles on the other hand emphasize the power of capital and this is done through the expropriation of profit through exploitation of labour. No thought is given to justice, equity and morality. For the capitalist what justifies the means is profit while for Marxism it is the satisfaction of the generality of the citizens.

In Nigeria, the presidential system of government is skewed to favour the elite and the "money bags" otherwise called godfathers. In this governmental system politics is seen as business where people invest little and reap humongously. This is why every person who has some reasonable education and cash jump the ship of private or public employment to join the bandwagon of politics. Scholars are leaving our tertiary institutions in droves to join politics. The political environment is becoming very tense and volatile. It has become the arena of winner takes all. The poor citizens have remained pawns in the chessboard of the political manipulation of politicians. Nobody thinks seriously about supplying the basic needs of the people. What accrues to the people come as accidental crumbs that slip off the tight fist of politicians. This is why we are advocating a rational blend of Marxism and capitalism.

A wholly Marxian system that emphasise welfarism will lead to lazy and unproductive citizenry that wait for government to do everything for them. On the other hand a thoroughbred capitalist system will produce aggressive, greedy and money-mongering citizenry that will value nothing but material acquisition. In this paper, the authors are concerned with achieving a rational integrated mixture of Marxism and capitalism. The goal is to achieve a policy that is characterized by the principle of live and let live, the sovereignty of the citizens, where the delivery of democracy dividends remains the justification of politicians occupying public office. According to Perry stone in *Breaking the Jewish Code*, the mystery of Jewish prosperity is found in the mixture of their capitalist and socialist orientations (11). The Jews are a hardworking people and also believe in helping to lift the downtrodden among them. The contrary is the case in Nigeria. The rich in Nigeria derive extra pleasure is subjugating, marginalizing and expropriating from the poor so as to keep them perpetually in subservience and under manipulative control.

Conclusion

In the words of Chinua Achebe nothing is wrong with our soil, atmosphere, land, environment nor even the human beings who populate Nigeria, the sole, problem is leadership. No good driver has ever emerged to drive Nigeria to safe havens of political stability, economic prosperity, social glory and spiritual emancipation. The problem perhaps, from this project of re-thinking may not be with presidentialism but with the human operators of the system and the ineluctable complicity of the ordinary citizens who have continued to allow the past and present leaders to take them for a ride. There is therefore need for immediate constitutional review which will take care of the many lapses and loopholes which our constitution contains which our leaders are heartlessly exploiting to continue the marginalization of all of us. Also, the electorate must arise from political limbo, slumber and passivity and assert their sovereignty in ensuring that leaders do what is right and are accountable for their actions.

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